

Lorentzian Curve Fitting Combined with DPP-BOTDA for Localized Heating Detection in Fiber-Optic Lines Exceeding 500 km with Remote Ends

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Abstract

In this paper, the detection of localized heating in a short segment of a fiber-optic communication line (FOCL) with a total length exceeding 500 km is demonstrated. The result was achieved by combining stimulated Brillouin scattering with two post-processing techniques: Lorentzian curve fitting (LCF) of the Brillouin gain spectrum and probabilistic heating detection based on kernel density estimation. A key design feature of the experimental setup is the use of two independent lasers, enabling measurements in long-haul lines with spatially separated ends. The fiber is divided into 50 km spans, between which bidirectional erbium-doped fiber amplifiers (B-EDFAs) are placed to compensate for propagation losses.

1. Methods

The method is based on Brillouin optical time-domain analysis (BOTDA) [1] and its modification, differential pulse-pair BOTDA (DPP-BOTDA) [2, 3]. In BOTDA, a continuous-wave probe is launched from one end of the fiber, while pump pulses are launched from the opposite end. Pump photons are scattered by acoustic phonons, producing a counter-propagating Stokes wave whose frequency shift with respect to the pump – the Brillouin frequency shift (BFS) – is unique to each fiber segment and sensitive to local temperature and strain.

When the frequency difference between probe and pump is swept, the Stokes wave is amplified through stimulated Brillouin scattering, forming the Brillouin gain spectrum (BGS). For a single-mode fiber the BGS follows a Lorentzian profile [4]:

$$G_B(\Delta\nu) = G_{\text{peak}} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{\delta\nu_B}{2}\right)^2}{(\Delta\nu - \Delta\nu_B)^2 + \left(\frac{\delta\nu_B}{2}\right)^2}, \quad (1)$$

where $G_B(\Delta\nu)$ is the Brillouin gain at frequency detuning $\Delta\nu$, G_{peak} is the peak gain, $\Delta\nu_B$ is the BFS, and $\delta\nu_B$ is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the spectrum. The BGS with Lorentzian fit is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: BGS of a standard SMF-28 fiber at room temperature without applied strain. BFS $\Delta\nu_B \approx 10.859$ GHz; FWHM $\delta\nu_B \approx 40$ MHz. Blue curve: Lorentzian fit (LCF); red dots: experimental data.

The BOTDA theoretical spatial resolution equals the pump pulse length. DPP-BOTDA improves it by acquiring two BGS traces with different pump pulse durations and subtracting them, yielding a spatial resolution equal to the pulse-length difference [2, 3].

Because of using two independent lasers, the frequency difference between them was fluctuating over time. To enable reliable spectral subtraction at each fiber position, every measured BGS was fitted with a Lorentzian (Eq. 1) before the subtraction step. This LCF procedure effectively suppresses noise and compensates frequency drifts during the measurement, yielding a substantially cleaner BFS profile along the fiber.

To further improve detection sensitivity, a heating probability was computed at every spatial point. This method is based on kernel density estimation (KDE) of the BFS noise distribution: a point is flagged as heated if its BFS deviates significantly from the noise-only distribution.

2. Results and Discussion

The measurement results are presented in Figure 2, where one can clearly observe the BFS difference profile (blue) and the heating probability curve (red) over the last 800 m

Figure 2: BFS difference profile (blue, left axis) and heating probability curve (red, right axis) over the terminal section of the 508 km line. The probability peak near 508.85 km corresponds to the 50 m heated segment.

of the 508 km line. A sharp probability peak at approximately 508.85 km unambiguously identifies a 50 m heated segment. The magnitude of the local BFS shift is consistent with the applied temperature increase of approximately 40 °C.

The experiment demonstrates that DPP-BOTDA can be successfully combined with Lorentzian fitting and probabilistic post-processing in long-haul fiber links.

The key results are as follows:

1. Localized heating of a 50 m fiber section was reliably detected in a FOCL exceeding 500 km with spatially separated ends and intermediate B-EDFA amplification.
2. The probabilistic KDE-based detection layer further enhances sensitivity and reduces the false-alarm rate.
3. LCF of the BGS significantly improves BFS estimation quality in the presence of inter-laser frequency drift, and is compatible with standard BOTDA as a noise-reduction post-processing step.

The results have many possible applications from monitoring long-haul communication infrastructure for physical-layer intrusion detection to structural health monitoring of civil engineering objects [5].

Additionally, the probabilistic heating detection method may be further used in long-haul sensing with low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) with prospects of applying to different parameters of BGS.

3. Conclusion

In this paper, the detection of localized heating in a 508 km fiber-optic line with spatially separated ends using DPP-BOTDA combined with Lorentzian curve fitting and probabilistic post-processing was demonstrated. The method does not require any modifications to the BOTDA hardware and is directly applicable to existing long-haul infrastructure.

References

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